

Women's Decision-Making Autonomy and Free and Informed Consent in Accessing Reproductive Health Care in Community Settings: A Qualitative Study in the N'djili Health Zone (Kinshasa City, Democratic Republic of the Congo)¹

Bertine Mbongopasi Ekeni

Doctoral School in Health Sciences, Higher Institute of Medical Techniques of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Higher Institute of Medical Techniques of Bandundu, Bandundu,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Koto-Te-Nyiwa Ngbolua

Department of Biology, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Center for Research in Pharmacopoeia and Traditional Medicine, Higher Institute of Medical
Techniques, Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo

Bernard Ntoto Nkunzi

Doctoral School in Health Sciences, Higher Institute of Medical Techniques of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Félicien Mukandu Basua Babintu

Doctoral School in Health Sciences, Higher Institute of Medical Techniques of Kinshasa, Kinshasa,
Democratic Republic of the Congo

Abstract

The aim of this study is to identify factors influencing the improvement of decision-making autonomy and free, informed consent among women in the N'djili Health Zone. A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from September 25 to October 26, 2022. Results revealed that participants faced challenges in exercising autonomy over reproductive health decisions, impacting their capacity to give informed consent. Additionally, a lack of information and awareness about reproductive health rights and options perpetuates existing inequalities. Developing educational and awareness programs that inform women of their rights, while

¹Address Author Correspondence to Koto-Te-Nyiwa Ngbolua at jpngbolua@unikin.ac.cd
Accepted: 12 November 2024 / Published online: 14 November 2024
© The Author(s), 2024. Paper ID, 100445.

involving the community and health professionals, are crucial to fostering sustainable change.

Keywords

Autonomy, decision, consent, reproductive health, N'djili..

1. Introduction

Community-based reproductive health care for women has long been a major public health concern. Indeed, access to reproductive health services is crucial to ensuring women's well-being and reducing health inequalities. However, many obstacles persist, particularly in terms of decision-making autonomy and women's free and informed consent to access reproductive healthcare (WHO, 2019).

Drawing on existing literature, we find that women face multiple challenges in accessing reproductive healthcare, including restrictive social norms, economic barriers and gaps in sex education. In addition, women's lack of decision-making autonomy and lack of respect for their consent are recurring issues that hinder equitable access to reproductive health services (Patel & Koenig, 2018).

According to reports from surveys carried out in Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) from 2015 to 2021, the family planning situation remains worrying. In fact, these reports showed that in 2010, only 5.4% of Congolese women in union were using a modern method of contraception, which is one of the lowest levels in Africa. Congolese women had an average of 6.3 children, whereas women in emerging countries have an average of two to three children. It is worth noting that 24% of Congolese women express an unmet need for family planning, i.e. they wish to space or stop having children, but curiously do not use any contraceptive method to avoid an unwanted pregnancy (WHO, 2023). However, in the community of the N'djili health zone, there are specific obstacles that may hinder the implementation of free and informed consent in women's access to reproductive health. These obstacles are social and cultural in nature. Research by Darebo et al (2024) has highlighted socio-cultural barriers, such as gender norms and traditional beliefs, which limit women's ability to make informed decisions about their reproductive health.

The aim of this study is to identify the elements to be taken into account in the design and implementation of a pilot program designed to strengthen the decision-making autonomy and consent of women aged 15 to 49 in the N'djili Health Zone in Kinshasa.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The N'djili Health Zone, located in the city-province of Kinshasa, is bounded to the north by Boulevard Lumumba, which separates it from the Masina I Health Zone; to the south by the large collector up to Quarter 10 and Kumbi Avenue up to Quarter 13, separating it from the Kimbanseke Health Zone; to the west by the Ndjili River, separating it from the Matete Health Zone to the northwest and the Kinseso Health Zone to the southwest; and finally to the east by the Nsanga River, which separates it from the Kingasani Health Zone.

2.2 Methods

This analytical cross-sectional study was conducted in the health areas of the N'djili Health Zone from September 25 to October 26, 2022. A qualitative, participatory approach was used, engaging women from the N'djili Health Zone. Data were collected through individual interviews (80 participants) and focus groups (10 participants). Qualitative data analysis provided an in-depth understanding of factors influencing women's autonomous decision-making and consent in reproductive health matters. Redundant responses appeared from the sixth participant onward, so the perspectives of the first nine participants were retained for analysis.

3. Results

3.1 Distribution of participants by socio-demographic characteristics

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of our participants.

Table 1. Distribution of participants by socio-demographic characteristics

Variable	Age	Education level	Marital status	Use of reproductive health services	Profession	Code
Participant 1	40 years old	A1	Bride	Active	Nutritionist	P1
Participant 2	37 years old	In the second cycle	Single	Active	Administrator Manager	P2
Participant 3	42 years old	L2	Bride	Active	Nurse supervisor	P3
Participant 4	39 years old	L2	Bride	Active	Accountant	P4
Participant 5	38 years old	D6	Single	Active	Housekeeper	P5
Participant 6	20 years	Licensing course	Single	Active	Student	P6
Participant 7	19 years old	D6	Single	Active	Housekeeper	P7
Participant 8	45 years old	L2	Bride	Active	Administrator Manager	P8
Participant 9	44 years old	D6	Bride	Active	Saleswoman	P9

This table presents demographic information and professional backgrounds of nine participants in the study, specifically focusing on age, education level, marital status, use of reproductive health services, profession, and participant code. The participants range in age from 19 to 45 years, with varying educational levels: three participants have a secondary school degree ("D6"), two have a first-cycle higher education qualification ("L2"), one has completed a licensing course, and one has an A1 diploma. In terms of marital status, five participants are married ("Bride"), and four are single. All participants actively use reproductive health services. Their professions vary, including roles such as nutritionist, administrator manager, nurse supervisor, accountant, housekeeper, student, and saleswoman, reflecting a mix of professional and household responsibilities. Each participant has been assigned a

unique code (P1 to P9) for identification in the study. This demographic diversity provides a comprehensive perspective on factors influencing autonomy and informed consent in reproductive health among women in the N'djili Health Zone.

3.2 Strengthening women's decision-making autonomy and free and informed consent to access reproductive health care

Table 2 summarizes the opinions collected on strengthening women's decision-making autonomy and free and informed consent for access to reproductive health care.

Table 2. Strengthening women's decision-making autonomy and free and informed consent to access reproductive health care

Sub-theme	Category	Verbatim
1. Awareness of autonomous decision-making and free, informed consent :	Organize information and awareness-raising sessions on women's reproductive health rights.	P3. Women believe in access to reproductive health education to make informed decisions about their own bodies. P6. Women believe that access to comprehensive, quality health education is a fundamental right. P9. Women are aware that reproductive health education can help prevent sexually transmitted diseases and unwanted pregnancies.
	- Train women to make decisions about their reproductive health.	P4. Women feel that reproductive health education helps break down the taboos and stigmas associated with sexuality. P5. Women see reproductive health education as essential to promoting women's autonomy and empowerment. P7. Women feel it's vital that men should also be made aware of reproductive health, for better mutual understanding.
	Institute communication campaigns to promote free and informed consent.	P1. Women think that reproductive health education should be included in school curricula from an early age. P2. Women recognize that reproductive health education contributes to family

		<p>planning and responsible motherhood/paternity.</p> <p>P8. Women stress the importance of raising awareness of sexual and reproductive rights to combat discrimination and gender-based violence.</p>
<p>2. Strengthening communication and negotiation skills :</p>	<p>- Organize communication and negotiation workshops to help women express their health needs and preferences.</p>	<p>P1. Women understand that promoting women's reproductive health is essential to their well-being and autonomy.</p> <p>P2. Women recognize the importance of their involvement in the governance of reproductive health services to ensure a needs-based approach.</p> <p>P3. Women feel that their experience as beneficiaries of reproductive health services can bring a unique perspective and innovative ideas to the governance of these services.</p>
	<p>- Train healthcare professionals to communicate respectfully and empathetically with women.</p>	<p>P4. Women want to be consulted and involved in decision-making on reproductive health policies to ensure an inclusive and equitable approach.</p> <p>P5. Women consider that inclusive and diversified governance of reproductive health services is necessary to meet the varied needs of women of all ages, backgrounds and situations.</p> <p>P6. Women understand that their active participation in the governance of reproductive health services can contribute to improving the quality of care and promoting women's health.</p>
	<p>- Encourage open dialogue and shared decision-making during medical consultations.</p>	<p>P7. Women recognize that involving women in the governance of reproductive health services can help identify and fill existing gaps in service provision.</p>

		<p>P8. Women feel that their participation in the governance of reproductive health services can strengthen the legitimacy and credibility of the decisions taken.</p> <p>P9. Women consider that their involvement in the governance of reproductive health services can promote a holistic and comprehensive approach to women's health.</p>
<p>3. Strengthening women's participation in health-related decision-making :</p>	<p>- Involve women in the design and implementation of reproductive health programs.</p>	<p>P4. Training women on their reproductive health rights to strengthen their ability to make autonomous, informed decisions.</p> <p>P7. Set up discussion and experience-sharing groups between women, to encourage exchange and empowerment.</p> <p>P8. Raising awareness of the importance of free and informed consent in reproductive health care, with an emphasis on respecting women's wishes.</p>
	<p>- Encourage the creation of women-led support and advocacy groups to defend their health rights.</p>	<p>P1. Psychological support for women who are victims of violence or family pressure, to help them make free decisions.</p> <p>P5. Set up a regular program monitoring and evaluation system to measure the impact of interventions and adjust actions according to identified needs.</p> <p>P6. Capacity-building for healthcare professionals on the importance of respecting women's decision-making autonomy, particularly in the area of reproductive health.</p>
	<p>- Set up feedback mechanisms so that women can express their needs and</p>	<p>P2. Creation of a listening and counseling space for women in economically precarious situations to</p>

	<p>concerns regarding reproductive health services.</p>	<p>remove financial obstacles to accessing reproductive health care.</p> <p>P3. Organization of information and awareness-raising sessions on contraception and family planning methods, emphasizing women's right to freely choose their contraceptive method.</p> <p>P9. Promote the participation of women in health-related decision-making bodies, to ensure that their needs and rights are adequately taken into account.</p>
--	---	--

The participants' responses demonstrate a profound understanding of the need to promote women's reproductive health and the value of their active involvement in reproductive health governance. They emphasize an inclusive approach focused on women's actual needs, incorporating their experiences as service users to enhance care quality and address service gaps. Testimonies reveal three main intervention areas to strengthen decision-making autonomy and free, informed consent: awareness-raising, communication skills, and inclusive decision-making. First, participants highlight the importance of information and awareness sessions to equip women with essential reproductive health knowledge for making informed choices, preventing STIs, avoiding unwanted pregnancies, and facilitating family planning. This need for awareness reflects existing inequalities in reproductive health information access, underscoring the importance of integrating these topics into educational curricula. Second, participants stress the need for communication workshops that build women's ability to express their health needs and engage in medical consultations effectively, along with training healthcare providers in respectful, empathetic communication to foster mutual respect. Lastly, participants call for women's involvement in designing and implementing reproductive health programs, proposing the creation of support and advocacy groups and feedback mechanisms to ensure responsiveness to their needs. Including women in health decision-making could bridge service gaps and foster a balanced approach to women's health. These insights reveal a shared view of decision-making autonomy as both a fundamental right and a tool for equality and quality-of-life improvement. Ultimately, participants advocate for policies that promote community involvement and educational initiatives that extend to men and healthcare professionals, aiming for long-term, transformative change.

3.3 Decision autonomy and free and informed consent when accessing reproductive health services in community settings

Table 3 shows what we heard about women's decision-making autonomy and free, informed consent to access reproductive health care in community settings.

Table 3. Decision-making autonomy and free and informed consent when accessing reproductive health services in community settings

Sub-theme	Category	Verbatim
1. Determinants of decision-making autonomy	- Social and family influence	P1. My family doesn't discuss sexuality, it's a taboo subject. P4. Pressure from family or partner, my in-laws forced me to have children even though I wasn't ready.
	- Reproductive health knowledge	P5. I've been told that condoms aren't natural. P6. Rumors about the side effects of contraceptives discouraged me from using them.
	- Access to information	P9. I haven't had any sex education, so I don't know how to protect my reproductive health.
	- Cultural and religious barriers	P1. Restrictive socio-cultural norms P2. Religious prohibitions, my religion considers contraception a sin, my religion advocates large families, so I don't have the right to limit births. P8. Women who take the pill are seen as immoral in my culture. P9. My community considers a woman who doesn't want children to be selfish, fear of community judgment
2. Interventions to promote autonomous decision-making :	Education and awareness	P1. Organize awareness-raising sessions on family planning and contraceptive methods. P3. Organize workshops to learn how to negotiate my

		contraceptive needs with my partner. P7. Organize awareness-raising campaigns on reproductive rights to find out about my rights and claim them.
	Strengthening decision-making capabilities	P4. Organize a self-esteem-building workshop to make decisions that benefit me. P10. Provide clear, accessible information on the various contraceptive methods available.
	Personalized support	P5. Organize psychological support to overcome family and cultural pressures. P9. Create women's support groups to share experiences and help each other.
	Training healthcare providers	P6. Organize training for healthcare professionals to make them more sensitive and informative about reproductive health. P2. Provide easy access to confidential and respectful reproductive health services.

These responses highlight the critical need for educational, social, and political interventions to empower women's decision-making in reproductive health. Family pressures, cultural taboos, and religious beliefs, such as the view that contraception is immoral or that women should have large families, create significant barriers to autonomy. Additionally, a lack of reproductive health knowledge and sex education, combined with myths about contraceptives, limits women's ability to make informed choices. To overcome these challenges, participants emphasized the importance of awareness-raising campaigns on family planning, reproductive rights, and contraceptive methods. They also advocated for workshops to build decision-making skills, enhance self-esteem, and enable women to negotiate contraceptive needs with their partners. The creation of women's support groups, psychological counseling to address cultural and familial pressures, and training for healthcare providers to ensure respectful, confidential services were also identified as crucial to promoting autonomy. These

responses underscore the need for comprehensive, multifaceted approaches combining education, empowerment, social support, and improved healthcare practices to strengthen women’s reproductive health decision-making autonomy.

3.4 Strengthening women's decision-making autonomy and free and informed consent to improve access to reproductive health services

Table 4 summarizes participants' views on empowering women and ensuring their free and informed consent in order to improve their access to reproductive health care.

Table 4. Strengthening women's decision-making autonomy and informed consent to improve access to reproductive health services

Sub-theme	Category	Verbatim
1. Strengthening decision-making and communication skills for women	1. Contraception	P2. High cost of contraceptives, lack of information on available options P3. Lack of information on different contraception methods P7. Lack of family support for family planning decisions P9. Lack of training for healthcare professionals on reproductive health issues
	2. Gynaecological consultations	P5. Long waits for an appointment with a gynaecologist
	3. Access to maternity care	P8. Social stigma surrounding early motherhood and difficulties accessing reproductive health services
	4. Sex education	P4. Cultural taboos around sexuality and contraception
	5. Post-abortion support	P9. Difficulty obtaining post-abortion care P1 Lack of health care facilities near where I live

The responses clearly reveal that women face multiple obstacles in accessing reproductive health and family planning services, with key barriers including a lack of information, high costs, cultural and social challenges, and logistical difficulties. These factors, such as insufficient knowledge about contraception,

the high price of contraceptives, and inadequate family support, hinder informed decision-making. Additionally, the lack of training for healthcare professionals on reproductive health issues, long waiting times for gynecological consultations, and the stigma surrounding early motherhood further complicate access to services. Cultural taboos on sexuality and contraception, along with the difficulty of accessing post-abortion care, also contribute to these challenges. These issues highlight the urgent need for comprehensive actions to ensure equitable access to reproductive health services, improve communication, and provide support that addresses both social and cultural barriers.

3.5 Strengthening decision-making and free and informed consent for women's reproductive health services in the N'djili Health Zone

Table 5 presents the participants' comments on enhancing decision-making and ensuring free and informed consent to improve women's reproductive health services.

Table 5. Strengthening decision-making and free and informed consent for women's reproductive health services in the N'djili health zone

Sub-theme	Category	Verbatim
1. Raising awareness and educating women about their reproductive health rights	Knowledge of reproductive health rights	P1. The right to information on contraception P2. The right to safe abortion P3. The right to quality pre- and post-natal care P4. The right to choose a contraceptive method P5. The right to a fulfilled sexual and reproductive life P6. The right to confidentiality of medical information P7. The right to informed consent for any medical treatment or intervention P8. The right to reproductive health services adapted to users' needs P9. The right to comprehensive sex education
2. Strengthening the skills of healthcare professionals to ensure informed consent	Communication with customers	P1. I expect healthcare professionals to be trained in patient rights and applicable laws.

		<p>P2. I would like healthcare professionals to be able to communicate clearly and empathetically when explaining the risks and benefits of treatment.</p> <p>P3. I would like healthcare professionals to take the time to answer all my questions and make sure I have understood the information provided.</p> <p>P4. It's important to me that healthcare professionals respect my decisions and don't pressure me into accepting treatment without my informed consent.</p> <p>P5. I want to feel confident that my doctor will respect my wishes.</p> <p>P6. Healthcare professionals must be made aware of cultural diversity and the specific needs of different patient groups.</p> <p>P7. Ongoing training for healthcare professionals on informed consent is essential to ensure quality care.</p> <p>P8. I'm convinced that strengthening healthcare professionals' informed consent skills will improve the relationship of trust with patients.</p> <p>P9. Healthcare professionals should be trained to recognize signs of non-consent and to respect patients' wishes.</p>
--	--	---

<p>3. Evaluation of the program's impact on access to reproductive health services</p>	<p>Informed consent practices</p>	<p>P2. I follow the improvement of access to contraceptives: better availability in health centers, free access to contraceptives thanks to the program, more choice of contraceptive methods.</p> <p>P3. I would like to have easier access to family planning services: introduction of information and awareness-raising sessions, reduction in waiting times, greater confidentiality in consultations.</p> <p>P4. I want to improve access to STI screening services: increased availability of tests, awareness of the importance of screening, support in the screening process.</p> <p>P5. I would like to have Easy access to safe abortion services: reduction of legal barriers, availability of pre- and post-abortion counseling, access to specialized clinics.</p> <p>P6. I want to improve access to maternal health services: better advice and follow-up during pregnancy, access to prenatal examinations, easier access to post-partum care.</p> <p>P7. Desired improvements to facilitate access to reproductive health services: reduction in costs, increase in the number of</p>
--	-----------------------------------	--

		<p>health centers, training of health personnel in reproductive health.</p> <p>P8. I would like to see the positive influence of the program on reproductive health: better knowledge of one's body, making informed decisions about reproductive health, reduced risk of complications during pregnancy.</p> <p>P9. I've noticed several differences since participating in the program: greater confidence in accessing reproductive health services, better communication with health staff, reduction in the number of incidents related to reproductive health.</p>
--	--	--

Participants demonstrate a good understanding of their reproductive health rights, yet it remains essential to enhance their access to information and services to facilitate autonomous and informed decision-making. Overcoming socio-cultural and economic barriers is crucial to enabling the full exercise of these rights. The responses underscore the importance of equipping healthcare professionals with specific skills to ensure informed consent, emphasizing the need for clear communication, respect for patient autonomy, and awareness of cultural diversity. Continuous training is also necessary to foster a patient-centered approach that builds trust and empowers patients to make informed choices about their reproductive health. The responses highlight the critical role of education and healthcare professional training in improving access to reproductive health services. Participants advocate for comprehensive information, particularly regarding contraception, safe abortion, and quality maternal care. They stress the importance of accessible, empathetic communication and a commitment to respecting patient autonomy and cultural differences. Ongoing training for healthcare providers in informed consent practices is seen as essential to ensuring that patients are well-informed about the risks and benefits of treatment options, thereby enhancing patient satisfaction and autonomy. Furthermore, participants reported improvements in the availability of contraceptives, family planning, and maternal health services, as well as easier access to safe abortion services and STI screening. These improvements reflect the positive impact of the program on reproductive health access. However,

there remains a need to address remaining barriers, such as legal restrictions, costs, and waiting times, while continuing to expand healthcare professional training. These efforts will further enhance the accessibility and quality of reproductive health services, helping to foster greater confidence among women in accessing the care they need.

4. Discussion

Access to reproductive healthcare is a fundamental right for all women, yet it remains heavily influenced by socio-economic and cultural factors. This study sheds light on the challenges faced by women in Kinshasa's N'djili health zone in exercising decision-making autonomy and providing free and informed consent when accessing reproductive health services. Decision-making autonomy is crucial for women to independently choose the reproductive health services they wish to utilize. However, this study highlights the significant social and economic barriers that undermine this autonomy. The majority of participants reported being influenced by cultural and family norms, which shape their reproductive choices. These findings align with the work of Benson et al. (2020), which emphasizes the impact of family and community pressures on women's ability to make independent decisions regarding their reproductive health. Free and informed consent is a cornerstone of human rights and medical ethics, ensuring that individuals are fully informed of the risks, benefits, and alternatives before making healthcare decisions (WHO, 2018). However, this study reveals that a large number of women in N'djili do not receive the necessary information to make informed choices. Healthcare providers, often constrained by limited resources, fail to provide the time and attention required for effective patient education (Kinsella, 2019). This lack of adequate information can result in poorly informed decisions, compromising the quality of care and women's health outcomes (Fathallah, 2021). This study underscores the critical need for addressing the socio-economic and cultural factors that limit women's autonomy in reproductive healthcare. While informed consent is a key principle of patient rights, the lack of resources and training for healthcare professionals in N'djili contributes to a cycle of limited access to quality information. Strengthening healthcare infrastructure, promoting patient education, and advocating for cultural and family norm changes are necessary steps to ensure that women can fully exercise their reproductive rights.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to identify key factors for improving decision-making autonomy and ensuring free and informed consent for women in the N'djili Health Zone in Kinshasa. The findings suggest that targeted interventions, such as reproductive health education programs and initiatives to challenge and change social norms, are necessary to empower women. Additionally, it is crucial to enhance the training of healthcare professionals on the importance of informed consent to ensure that patients are adequately informed and can make empowered decisions. It is also recommended that longitudinal studies be conducted to track changes in women's autonomy and access to reproductive healthcare over time, considering socio-economic and political factors. Based on these findings, it is imperative for policy-makers to integrate these insights into public health policies that prioritize equitable access to reproductive health services, promote women's autonomy, and address the socio-cultural barriers that

restrict decision-making in reproductive health. Furthermore, strategies should include the development of programs that raise awareness among both women and healthcare providers about the importance of informed consent, alongside community-based initiatives that address and modify restrictive social norms.

Acknowledgments

The authors are extended to the authorities of the N'djili Health Zone, particularly Dr. Bolamba Ghelogo Edouard, for their invaluable support.

References

1. Benson, C., Smith, J., & Wang, L. (2020). Influence of Societal Norms on Women's Decision-Making in Reproductive Health. *Journal of Women's Health*, 29(3), 350-358.
2. Darebo, T. D., Birhanu, Z., Alemayehu, M., Balcha, B., Worku, A., Assele, D. D., & Spigt, M. (2024). Utilization of sexual and reproductive health services among construction worker women in southern Ethiopia. *BMC Women's Health*, 24(1), 201
3. Fathallah, Y., Lemoine, F., & Hage, M. (2021). Education, Empowerment and Reproductive Health: A Study among Women in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Health Services*, 51(2), 123-135.
4. Kinsella, S. (2019). *Challenges in Provid*. Unpublished.
5. WHO. (2023). *Importance of human rights in family planning*. Geneva, WHO.
6. Patel, V., & Koenig, M. A. (2018). The political economy of women's reproductive health and family planning in India. *Studies in Family Planning*, 49(3), 247-263.
7. WHO. (2018). *Ensuring Respect for Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights*. Geneva, WHO.
8. WHO. (2019). *Autonomy, consent, and reproductive rights: A global perspective*. Geneva: WHO.